

Questionnaire:

USER 1

Usability Test Experience:

1. How would you rate your overall experience with the online collaboration tool from 1-10? Give a brief explanation as well:

10/10
It was a fun experience. There were some confusing elements, but it was very usable after those things were figured out.

2. Were you able to easily navigate through the features of the tool? Was it intuitive to navigate without any complications? Answer with a 1-10 + explanation.

8. The only thing that was bad about navigation was the menu in the top left corner. The hover-to-open animation was slow.

3. Did you encounter any technical difficulties while using the tool? If yes, please describe:

Rate limit on code execution API. Realtime sync stopped working for a brief moment.

Collaboration Experience:

1. Did you find the overall collaborative coding experience efficient and productive?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		x

2. Were you able to effectively communicate and coordinate with your group members?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		x

3. How would you rate the performance and responsiveness of the collaborative features (real-time editing)?

Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
	x		

Suggestions for Improvement:

1. What features or functionalities would you like to see added or improved in the online collaboration tool? (If there are any)

Multiple coding tabs for the different parts in the exercises to the user doesn't have to delete code.

AI code help

Don't have shared undo redo history

2. Do you have any suggestions for enhancing the user interface or user experience?

Play buttons green and more descriptive.

Loading indicators for when code is being executed

Overall Impression:

1. Do you think a fully fledged version of this web application would be viable in a learning environment such as the one at AAU?

Yes. However, the users will miss out on knowledge about Cmake and how to configure their IDE, which is essential.

2. Any additional comment or feedback you would like to add?

No

Questionnaire:

USER 2

Usability Test Experience:

1. How would you rate your overall experience with the online collaboration tool from 1-10? Give a brief explanation as well:

5, ran into some bugs and the collaborative part of the program feels a bit unnecessary with such simple code examples

2. Were you able to easily navigate through the features of the tool? Was it intuitive to navigate without any complications? Answer with a 1-10 + explanation.

5, would have been nice with some explanations of what the different buttons do and what code language we are supposed to use

3. Did you encounter any technical difficulties while using the tool? If yes, please describe:

yes it stopped working

Collaboration Experience:

1. Did you find the overall collaborative coding experience efficient and productive?

Yes	No	Somewhat
	x	

2. Were you able to effectively communicate and coordinate with your group members?

Yes	No	Somewhat
x		

3. How would you rate the performance and responsiveness of the collaborative features (real-time editing)?

Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
x			

Suggestions for Improvement:

1. What features or functionalities would you like to see added or improved in the online collaboration tool? (If there are any)

2. Do you have any suggestions for enhancing the user interface or user experience?

add explanations to what different buttons does (2 run buttons i still dont know

what the function of the button at the code is?)
add color to the run buttons - they kind look like they are inactive

Overall Impression:

1. Do you think a fully fledged version of this web application would be viable in a learning environment such as the one at AAU?

yes

2. Any additional comment or feedback you would like to add?

no

Questionnaire:

USER 3

Usability Test Experience:

1. How would you rate your overall experience with the online collaboration tool from 1-10? Give a brief explanation as well:

5. The overall experience is a solid 5. You make a user and go to the same exercise as your classmates. It works alright, but there are some bugs and the UI could be improved in the sense of having more overview.

2. Were you able to easily navigate through the features of the tool? Was it intuitive to navigate without any complications? Answer with a 1-10 + explanation.

A solid 4. There are a lot of times where you are not entirely sure if the website is reacting to your input. The UI could also be improved. It is somewhat overcomplicated. You can go into a lecture, and then there is a completely new page for the exercises. It could possibly be in the same window. The Simpler the better.

3. Did you encounter any technical difficulties while using the tool? If yes, please describe:

Yes it stopped updating at some point so i had to refresh.

Collaboration Experience:

1. Did you find the overall collaborative coding experience efficient and productive?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		X

2. Were you able to effectively communicate and coordinate with your group members?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		X

3. How would you rate the performance and responsiveness of the collaborative features (real-time editing)?

Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
	X		

Suggestions for Improvement:

1. What features or functionalities would you like to see added or improved in the online collaboration tool? (If there are any)

The main button should be a click, not a hover.

2. Do you have any suggestions for enhancing the user interface or user experience?

I'm not sure if the program knows that I click the compile button. It is not clear that the console is the console and the Tests are the Tests.

Overall Impression:

1. Do you think a fully fledged version of this web application would be viable in a learning environment such as the one at AAU?

Definitely! If the website is fully functional, it will definitely make it easier for people to learn to program. If it continues to be like it is right now it will definitely make it way more difficult to learn to program. It should say what programming language you are programming in. Intellisense? Maybe also some tips and tricks if you are stuck.

2. Any additional comment or feedback you would like to add?

Grammarly makes it look like the printf is wrong since it wants to change it to print

Questionnaire:

USER 4

Usability Test Experience:

1. How would you rate your overall experience with the online collaboration tool from 1-10? Give a brief explanation as well:

While trying this tool i started comparing it to other finished and alike products, some of these are: Codewars, leetcode and etc.
Comparing the prototype product to these finished products would net a score of 2

Looking at the product for itself it would get a much higher score of 7.

Many, if not all, of the tools worked like they had to. The execution button for the code needs something for instant feedback else it could result in spamming the button.

Navigating through the courses and exercises was fine.

Having to work together in collaboration with other people is problematic when having to edit the same code. I would rather that you could divide the exercises into how many members there are and each could do a part of the code somehow.

2. Were you able to easily navigate through the features of the tool? Was it intuitive to navigate without any complications? Answer with a 1-10 + explanation.

Having no instant feedback on the running of the code was a setback. It could result in spamming the button because not result or loading would appear.

Some of the lectures were not sorted correctly 3>5>4 other than that navigation worked fine. Loading times were not something that impacted ones experience either.

A thing that would be nice is having a text that says "This is the tests" and "This is your console output".

3. Did you encounter any technical difficulties while using the tool? If yes, please describe:

Yes, some of the error codes following the code were almost unreadable. This was probably due to how the API responds and with some special characters.

The UI relies on very dark colors, this in turn makes it very difficult to see any icons that the ui may display in its place.

Collaboration Experience:

1. Did you find the overall collaborative coding experience efficient and productive?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		x

2. Were you able to effectively communicate and coordinate with your group members?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		x

3. How would you rate the performance and responsiveness of the collaborative features (real-time editing)?

Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
		x	

Suggestions for Improvement:

1. What features or functionalities would you like to see added or improved in the online collaboration tool? (If there are any)

Not having a shared undo/redo history.

I would like to see exercises split for each user in a "team" so you don't keep editing the same part of the code. (This is a very personal opinion on how code collaboration should work)

2. Do you have any suggestions for enhancing the user interface or user experience?

More vibrant colors

as i described earlier some indication which text field is what like "Tests" and "Console"

Overall Impression:

1. Do you think a fully fledged version of this web application would be viable in a learning environment such as the one at AAU?

Yes.

When the features of the tool are all finished i think it could be a great edition.

2. Any additional comment or feedback you would like to add?

No.

Questionnaire:

USER 5

Usability Test Experience:

1. How would you rate your overall experience with the online collaboration tool from 1-10? Give a brief explanation as well:

8 : nice user interface, easy to use

2. Were you able to easily navigate through the features of the tool? Was it intuitive to navigate without any complications? Answer with a 1-10 + explanation.

7: menu button, please make it clickable (not just hover). Easy to navigate. I did not know that I had to check the exercise before running the code.

3. Did you encounter any technical difficulties while using the tool? If yes, please describe:

API can run out

Collaboration Experience:

1. Did you find the overall collaborative coding experience efficient and productive?

Yes	No	Somewhat
x		

2. Were you able to effectively communicate and coordinate with your group members?

Yes	No	Somewhat
x		

3. How would you rate the performance and responsiveness of the collaborative features (real-time editing)?

Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
		x	

Suggestions for Improvement:

1. What features or functionalities would you like to see added or improved in the online collaboration tool? (If there are any)

- clickable menu button
- display user
- display lecture nr

2. Do you have any suggestions for enhancing the user interface or user experience?

- light and dark theme
- sign out - place in right top corner

Overall Impression:

1. Do you think a fully fledged version of this web application would be viable in a learning environment such as the one at AAU?

yes, nice everything is in the same place

2. Any additional comment or feedback you would like to add?

no

Questionnaire:

USER 6

Usability Test Experience:

1. How would you rate your overall experience with the online collaboration tool from 1-10? Give a brief explanation as well:

7 - nice UI

2. Were you able to easily navigate through the features of the tool? Was it intuitive to navigate without any complications? Answer with a 1-10 + explanation.

7: a little funky, but with a little guidance it was fine

3. Did you encounter any technical difficulties while using the tool? If yes, please describe:

yes, the api had a timeout

Collaboration Experience:

1. Did you find the overall collaborative coding experience efficient and productive?

Yes	No	Somewhat
x		

2. Were you able to effectively communicate and coordinate with your group members?

Yes	No	Somewhat
		x

3. How would you rate the performance and responsiveness of the collaborative features (real-time editing)?

Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
	x		

Suggestions for Improvement:

1. What features or functionalities would you like to see added or improved in the online collaboration tool? (If there are any)

display users in the top, as well as display the lecture number.

2. Do you have any suggestions for enhancing the user interface or user experience?

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Overall Impression:

1. Do you think a fully fledged version of this web application would be viable in a learning environment such as the one at AAU?

sure, it's nice to have

2. Any additional comment or feedback you would like to add?